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ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ
JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ДАВРИЙЛИГИ: 2016-2026

ЖИЛД 11
СОҢ 2

2026

ЧОП
ЭТИЛГАН САНА:
20.04.2026

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

11 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 11, НОМЕР 2

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VOLUME 11, ISSUE 2

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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

УДК: 616.74-022-002.4

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FOURNIER GANGRENE (CASE REPORT)

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19816924>

ANNOTATION

To date, Fournier's gangrene remains an insufficiently studied acute surgical disease of a purulent-necrotic nature. This pathology represents one of the rare forms of infectious necrotizing fasciitis of the genital and perineal regions with polymicrobial etiology. The prevalence of Fournier's gangrene as a life-threatening surgical condition has been increasing annually. The disease is characterized by a rapid clinical course accompanied by signs of severe intoxication. In most cases, the outcome depends on the timing of surgical intervention from the onset of the disease. Timely diagnosis, prompt surgical treatment, and adequate antibiotic therapy can significantly reduce the incidence of complications and mortality.

Keywords: Fournier's gangrene, lightning gangrene of the scrotum, skin plastics

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АННОТАЦИЯ

На сегодняшний день гангрена Фурнье остается недостаточно изученным острым хирургическим заболеванием гнойно-некротического характера. Данная патология представляет собой одну из редких форм инфекционного некротизирующего фасциита гениталий и промежности полимикробной этиологии. Распространенность гангрены Фурнье, как опасной хирургической патологии, с каждым годом возрастает. Заболевание характеризуется стремительным течением, с явлениями выраженной интоксикации. Исход в большинстве случаев зависит от времени выполнения операции от начала возникновения заболевания. Своевременная диагностика, хирургическое лечение и адекватная антибиотикотерапия позволяют минимизировать частоту осложнений и летальность.

Ключевые слова: гангрена Фурнье, молниеносная гангрена мошонки, кожная пластика

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FURNE GANGRENASI (AMALIYOTDAN OLINGAN HOLAT)

ANNOTATSIYA

Bugungi kunga qadar Furne gangrenasi, o'tkir jarrohlik kasalligining yiringli-nekrotik turi bo'lib, yetarlicha o'rganilmagan bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu patologiya jinsiy a'zolar va perineumning infeksiyon nekrotik fassitining kam uchraydigan polimikrob etiologik shakllaridan biridir. Furne gangrenasining tarqalishi xavfli jarrohlik patologiyasi sifatida har yili ortib bormoqda. Kasallik kuchli intoksikatsiya belgilar bilan tez kechishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Natija ko'p hollarda kasallikning boshlanishidan boshlab operatsiya vaqtiga bog'liq. O'z vaqtida tashxis qo'yish, jarrohlik davolash va yetarli antibiotik terapiyasi asoratlar darajasini va o'lim holatlarini minimallashtirishi mumkin.

Keywords: Fournier's gangrene, fulminant gangrene of the scrotum, skin plastic surgery

Fulminant gangrene of the perineum, or Fournier's gangrene (FG), is a specific form of necrotizing fasciitis of polymicrobial etiology, localized primarily in the perineum, penis, and scrotum. This disease is rare and poorly understood, but it is a rather acute and dangerous surgical pathology in modern medical practice. According to statistics, there has been an increase in purulent-septic lesions of the soft tissues of the perineum, with the incidence of FG increasing 2.3-6.5 times over the past decade.

It is believed that these figures are due to the increasing number of patients with immunodeficiency [1, 2, 7, 8].

According to global statistics, FG occurs in 1.6 cases per 100,000 men annually, accounting for approximately 0.1% of all hospitalizations in surgical departments. This pathology most often affects men aged 50-70 years, who also have concomitant diseases. In females, Fournier's gangrene is quite rare and accounts for less than 1% of all cases of the disease. According to the results of the study by E.B. Benjelloun et al., the ratio of men and women with GF is 10:1, while the average age of patients with GF is determined to be 50.9 years [6]. N. Vayvada et al. published data on the disease of GF in a child from 21 days old and patients over 70 years old [10, 11]. The incidence of GF is not characterized by seasonality and endemicity, however, it should be noted that the highest rates of GF incidence are determined in Asian and African countries, in comparison with European countries and the USA [3, 5, 9]. Immunocompromised patients are most susceptible to developing GF, specifically those with a history of diabetes mellitus (32-66%) and chronic alcoholism (25-66%). Obesity, malignant neoplasms, and drug addiction can also be predisposing factors.

Local predisposing factors are based on the characteristics of anogenital anatomy, in particular, the relative thinness of the skin and increased moisture in the scrotum with loose and poorly developed subcutaneous fat, the close proximity of the urethra to the possible seeding of pathogens, and the anal opening, which contributes to the flora of the anal canal, skin of the scrotum, perineum [3, 4, 5].

Today, the etiology of GF can be determined in 95-97% of cases. GF may develop following trauma to the perineum or with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the colon, which occurs in 30-50% of cases. Purulent-inflammatory processes in the urogenital area, scrotum, and perineum also lead to GF in 20-40% of patients. The predominant cause of GF is a perianal abscess, occurring in 67-82% of all patients with GF [4, 9].

According to the results of a comparative analysis by Perkins et al., in the pathogenesis of GF, the proportion of aerobic flora exceeds anaerobic flora, due to pathogens of the intestinal group, namely *E. coli*, *Proteus*, and *Pseudomonas* [8, 10].

Today, the issues of early diagnosis and treatment strategies for GF, using new adjuvant therapy methods, clinical and laboratory parameters, and the prognosis of treatment, which determine its development and outcome, are relevant. Below is a clinical observation from our own practice, in accordance with the ethical standards of the Helsinki Declaration of the World Medical Association (2008).

Patient D.U., 40, was admitted to the private medical center "SAKHOVATBU" in Tashkent on a planned basis.

He presented with complaints upon admission of an extensive postoperative wound in the perineum, absence of scrotal skin between the penis and anus, and a change in the position of both testicles toward the inguinal canal, pain when walking and sitting, and decreased potency. According to his medical history, the patient had undergone surgery two months earlier at a multidisciplinary medical center in the Bukhara region with a diagnosis of acute ischeorectal paraproctitis. He had previously undergone three surgeries for this condition.

Local status: the external genitalia are normally developed, there is no skin in the perineum, on both testicles and under the penis, there is an extensive granulating wound measuring 17x15 cm, with pronounced hyperemia around it (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. External appearance of the genitals of patient D., 40 years old. Extensive granulating wounds of the perineum, inguinal areas and both testicles.

Laboratory tests: Complete blood count: leukocytes - 9.8-9.5-9.6-8.0-7.8-7.7x10⁹/L.

Coagulogram: fibrinogen - 4.92-4.85-4.79-4.01 g/L; thrombotest - 7-6-6-5; INR - 1.25-1.25-1.22-1.18. Other test results were within normal limits.

Based on clinical, laboratory, and instrumental data, the patient was diagnosed with Fournier's gangrene. Extensive granulating wounds of the perineum, inguinal areas, and both testicles were present.

After appropriate preoperative preparation, the patient underwent surgery (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Fascial plastic surgery of the perineum, groin area and testicles.

The postoperative course was satisfactory. The patient received comprehensive treatment, and daily wound dressings were applied. The postoperative wound healed by secondary intention. Bacteriological examination No. 205.

Conclusion: Staphylococcus haemolyticus.

Complete recovery with tissue healing and restoration of the patient's physical condition occurred after 35 days.

The patient was discharged in satisfactory condition. A follow-up examination revealed satisfactory wound healing and the patient's condition.

Conclusion: Fournier's gangrene remains a rapidly progressing and life-threatening condition. Effective management requires a multidisciplinary approach involving surgeons, proctologists, urologists, and intensive care specialists. Early diagnosis and a comprehensive treatment strategy—including timely surgical intervention, combination antibacterial therapy, infusion therapy, immunocorrection, and improvement of blood rheology—are essential for achieving favorable outcomes in patients with Fournier's gangrene.

Acknowledgements

This case report was supported by the administration and staff of the private medical center "SAKHOVATBU."

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